

Optimization of Hybrid Machining Processes through Laser Structuring for Enhanced Titanium Alloy Machinability

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Abstract: This study developed and optimized hybrid machining processes by integrating laser structuring with micro-milling and micro-grinding to improve the machinability of titanium alloys. Key findings include the significant reduction of cutting forces and enhanced process efficiency through optimal laser parameters, which minimized thermal damage and improved tool performance. The results demonstrate the potential of laser structuring to advance precision machining, particularly for complex and hard-to-machine materials. This research provides a foundation for more efficient manufacturing strategies in high-precision applications.

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I. Introduction

Titanium alloys, particularly Ti6Al4V, are critical in aerospace, biomedical, and automotive sectors due to their high strength-to-weight ratio, corrosion resistance, and biocompatibility, but these same properties lead to significant machining challenges, including rapid tool wear, high cutting forces, and poor surface integrity [1]. Traditional methods like milling and grinding often struggle to meet the precision and surface quality demands, particularly for complex geometries [2]. Hybrid machining processes, which combine conventional methods with advanced technologies like laser assistance, have emerged as a promising solution [3]. Ultrashort pulse lasers (USPL) are especially advantageous for micro structuring and surface modification, as they ablate material with minimal thermal damage, maintaining workpiece integrity [4].

This study develops and optimizes a hybrid machining process that integrates laser structuring with precision milling and grinding, with a focus on how laser parameters affect material removal, surface quality, and machining forces. It also considers titanium alloys produced through selective laser melting (SLM). The research aims to establish a robust process that improves the machinability of titanium alloys, achieving high precision and surface quality, and addressing the limitations of traditional machining methods in modern manufacturing.

II. Material and methods

The study aimed to develop high-precision hybrid machining processes for titanium materials by combining milling, grinding, and laser structuring techniques. Using extruded titanium and selectively laser melted (SLM) titanium, specific tools like solid carbide mini-grooving end mills and diamond grinding pins were selected in collaboration with project partners. Advanced equipment,

including the KERN Pyramid Nano CNC machining center and TRUMPF TruMicro 5050 ultrashort pulse laser, was used for experiments (Fig. 1). Initial benchmarking identified optimal machining parameters, leading to the integration of laser assistance in milling and grinding processes. The laser structuring parameters were optimized to reduce thermal damage and tool wear, focusing on machining forces, surface roughness, and subsurface changes. A two-temperature model was used to simulate heat development, predicting temperature evolution and material ablation during laser processing. Post-machining analyses, including surface roughness, microhardness, and residual stress evaluations, assessed the impact of laser structuring. Statistical methods ensured the reliability and repeatability of results, leading to an optimized hybrid machining process that effectively combines laser structuring with precision milling and grinding, addressing the challenges associated with machining titanium.

Figure 1: a) Schematic structure of the laser integration, b) KERN machine tool and integrated laser, c) Laser position and laser beam guidance

III. Results and discussion

The study focused on developing and analyzing high-precision hybrid machining processes that integrate milling, grinding, and laser assistance for titanium alloys, including both conventionally produced and additively manufactured components.

Laser-assisted micro-milling of Ti6Al4V using a Yb:YAG picosecond laser showed that pre-machining surface structuring significantly reduced cutting forces. This effect was notably due to a decrease in the heat-affected zone (HAZ) with increased laser scan speeds, which minimized thermal damage such as material melting. At an optimal scan speed of 600 mm/s, efficient material removal was achieved with minimal tool wear, addressing the common issue of high adhesion wear in micro-milling titanium after laser structuring.

Comparative studies of additively manufactured (SLM) and conventionally produced (extruded) Ti6Al4V parts revealed no significant differences in machinability regarding cutting forces during micro-milling and micro-grinding. As shown in Fig. 2, both types of parts exhibited similar cutting forces across various feed rates and cutting speeds. However, surface roughness varied, with conventionally produced parts generally having higher roughness compared to the additively manufactured parts, which displayed discontinuities due to the additive process.

Figure 2: Influence of feed per tooth and cutting speed on the machining forces for a) heat-treated SLM, b) non-heat-treated SLM, and c) extruded parts

Laser structuring of workpiece surfaces led to a notable reduction in cutting forces during micro-milling, as illustrated in Fig. 3. This decrease was primarily due to the removal of material through laser ablation, which reduced the maximum chip thickness. Additionally, the structured surfaces lowered overall machining forces by reducing chip volume during tool-workpiece contact. Key structuring parameters, including the density and depth of the laser patterns, were crucial in optimizing the process by reducing force requirements and improving surface finish quality.

Figure 3: Influence of structure density on the reduction of cutting forces at different feed rates per tooth

The study found that laser structuring of workpiece surfaces significantly reduced grinding forces in micro-

grinding. This reduction was due to a smaller contact area between the abrasive grains and the workpiece, facilitated by the laser-induced surface structuring. The high laser scan speed used to create these structures minimized thermal damage, resulting in lower resistance during grinding. Moreover, the microstructural changes caused by the laser, including reduced hardness in the heat-affected zone, eased material removal. Consequently, the structured surfaces required less grinding force and showed better surface integrity, with minimal tool wear. This indicates that laser structuring effectively improves the efficiency and precision of micro-grinding, especially for hard-to-grind materials like Ti6Al4V (Fig. 4).

Figure 4: Influence of the structured grinding wheel on the grinding forces

IV. Conclusions

This research effectively developed and optimized high-precision hybrid machining processes by combining laser structuring with micro-milling and micro-grinding. The findings show that laser structuring significantly reduces cutting forces and improves material machinability, especially for titanium alloys. The analysis revealed that optimal laser parameters, such as scanning speed and power, are essential for minimizing thermal damage and enhancing machining efficiency. The study also emphasized the importance of tool conditioning and simulation modeling for predicting outcomes and ensuring high-quality results. These insights could lead to more efficient and precise machining strategies for complex and hard-to-machine materials.

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